

Realize Engineering

An engineering commentary for everyone every Wednesday since 2012

@ www.RealizeEngineering.blog

DIMES posts

A series of posts from the Realize Engineering blog describing activities associated with the DIMES (Development of Integrated MEasurement Systems) that were published between January 2019 and October 2021.

The [University of Liverpool](http://www.liverpool.ac.uk) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd.](#) [Airbus](#) is the topic manager on behalf of the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking.

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in these blog posts reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information they contain.

Contents

Finding DIMES	3
Archive video footage from EU projects.....	5
Joining the dots.....	6
Some problem in a different language	8
When seeing nothing is a success.....	9
Condition-monitoring using infrared imaging	10
Turning the screw in dentistry	12
My Engineering Day	14
Most valued player performs remote installation.....	16
Out of the valley of death into a hype cycle?	17
An upside to lockdown.....	19
Noisy progressive failure of a composite panel.....	20
Our last DIMES	21
Too much of a good thing?	22

Finding DIMES

A couple of weeks ago I wrote about the ‘INSTRUCTIVE final reckoning’ (see post on January 9th). INSTRUCTIVE was an EU project, which ended on December 31st, 2018 in which we demonstrated that infra-red cameras could be used to monitor the initiation and propagation of cracks in aircraft structures (see Middleton et al, 2019). Now, we have seamlessly moved on to a new EU project, called DIMES (Development of Integrated MEasurement Systems), which started on January 1st, 2019. To quote our EU documentation, the overall aim of DIMES is ‘to develop and demonstrate an automated measurement system that integrates a range of measurement approaches to enable damage and cracks to be detected and monitored as they originate at multi-material interfaces in an aircraft assembly’. In simpler terms, we are going to take the results from the INSTRUCTIVE project, integrate them with other existing technologies for monitoring the structural health of an aircraft, and produce a system that can be installed in an aircraft fuselage and will provide early warning on the formation of cracks. We have two years to achieve this target and demonstrate the system in a ground-based test on a real fuselage at an Airbus facility. This was a scary prospect until we had our kick-off meeting and a follow-up brainstorming session a couple of weeks ago. Now, it’s a little less scary. If I have scared you with the prospect of cracks in aircraft, then do not be alarmed; we have been flying aircraft with cracks in them for years. It is impossible to build an aircraft without cracks appearing, possibly during manufacturing and certainly in service – perfection (i.e. cracklessness) is unattainable and instead the stresses are maintained low enough to ensure undetected cracks will not grow (see ‘Alan Arnold Griffith’ on April 26th, 2017) and that detected ones are repaired before they propagate significantly (see ‘Aircraft inspection’ on October 10th, 2018).

I should explain that the ‘we’ above is the University of Liverpool and Strain Solutions Limited, who were the partners in INSTRUCTIVE, plus EMPA, the Swiss National Materials Laboratory, and Dantec Dynamics GmbH, a producer of scientific instruments in Ulm, Germany. I am already working with these latter two organisations in the EU project MOTIVATE; so, we are a close-knit team who know and trust each other – that’s one of the keys to successful collaborations tackling ambitious challenges with game-changing outcomes.

So how might the outcomes of DIMES be game-changing? Well, at the moment, aircraft are designed using computer models that are comprehensively validated using measurement data from a large number of expensive experiments. The MOTIVATE project is about reducing the number of experiments and increasing the quality and quantity of information gained from each experiment, i.e. ‘Getting Smarter’ (see post on June 21st 2017). However, if the measurement system developed in DIMES allowed us to monitor in-flight strain fields in critical locations on-board an aircraft, then we would have high quality data to support future design work, which would allow further reductions in the campaign of experiments required to support new designs; and we would have continuous comprehensive monitoring of the

structural integrity of every aircraft in the fleet, which would allow more efficient planning of maintenance as well as increased safety margins, or reductions in structural weight while maintaining safety margins. This would be a significant step towards digital twins of aircraft (see 'Fourth industrial revolution' on July 4th, 2018 and 'Can you trust your digital twin?' on November 23rd, 2016).

The INSTRUCTIVE, MOTIVATE and DIMES projects have received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 685777, No. 754660 and No. 820951 respectively.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Sources:

Middleton CA, Gaio A, Greene RJ & Patterson EA, [Towards automated tracking of initiation and propagation of cracks in Aluminium alloy coupons using thermoelastic stress analysis](#), J. Non-destructive Testing, 38:18, 2019

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [MOTIVATE project](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [computational modelling](#), [cracks](#), [design](#), [digital twin](#), [DIMES](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [infra-red](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [model validation](#), [MyResearch](#), [non-destructive inspection](#), [perfection](#), [research](#), [strain](#), [thermoelastic stress analysis](#) on [February 6, 2019](#).

Archive video footage from EU projects

This week I am in the US presenting work from our EU projects [INSTRUCTIVE](#) and [MOTIVATE](#) at the [Annual Conference and Exposition of the Society for Experimental Mechanics](#). Although the INSTRUCTIVE project was completed at the end of December 2018, the process of disseminating and exploiting the research will go on for some time. The capability to identify the initiation of cracks when they are less than 1mm long and to track their propagation is a key piece of technology for [DIMES project](#) in which we are developing an integrated system for monitoring the condition of aircraft structures. We are in the last twelve months of the MOTIVATE project and we have started producing video clips about the technology that is being developed. So, if you missed my presentations at the conference in the US then you can watch the videos online using the links below 😊.

We have been making videos describing the outputs of our EU project for about 20 years; so, if you want to see some vintage footage of me twenty years younger then watch a [video](#) from the INDUCE project that was active from 1998 to 2001.

MOTIVATE videos: [Introduction](#); Industrial calibration of DIC measurements [using a calibration plate](#) or [using an LCD screen](#)

The MOTIVATE project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 754660.

Image: Peppermill Hotel in Reno, Nevada where the conference is being held.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [mechanics](#), [MOTIVATE project](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [conferences](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [INDUCE](#), [INDUCE project](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [NDE](#), [NDT](#), [research](#), [science](#), [SEM](#), [videos](#) on [June 5, 2019](#).

Joining the dots

Six months ago, I wrote about '[Finding DIMES](#)' as we kicked off a new EU-funded project to develop an integrated measurement system for identifying and tracking damage in aircraft structures. We are already a quarter of the way through the project and we have a concept design for a modular measurement system based on commercial off-the-shelf components. We started from the position of wanting our system to provide answers to four of the five questions that Farrar & Worden [\[1\]](#) posed for structural health monitoring systems in 2007; and, in addition to provide information to answer the fifth question. The five questions are: Is there damage? Where is the damage? What kind of damage is present? How severe is the damage? And, how much useful life remains?

During the last six months our problem definition has evolved through discussions with our EU Topic Manager, Airbus, to four objectives, namely: to quantify applied loads; to provide condition-led/predictive maintenance; to find indications of damage in composites of 6mm diameter or greater and in metal to detect cracks longer than 1mm; and to provide a digital solution. At first glance there may not appear to be much connection between the initial problem definition and the current version; but actually, they are not very far apart although the current version is more specific. This evolution from the idealised vision to the practical goal is normal in engineering projects.

We plan to use point sensors, such as resistance strain gauges or fibre Bragg gratings, to quantify applied loads and track usage history; while imaging sensors will allow us to measure strain fields that will provide information about the changing condition of the structure using the image decomposition techniques developed in previous EU-funded projects: ADVISE, VANESSA (see '[Setting standards](#)' on January 29th, 2014) and [INSTRUCTIVE](#). We will use these techniques to identify and track cracks in metals [\[2\]](#); while for composites, we will apply a technique developed through an EPSRC iCASE award from 2012-16 on 'Full-field strain-based methods for NDT & structural integrity measurement' [\[3\]](#).

I gave a short briefing on DIMES to a group of Airbus engineers last month and it was good to see some excitement in the room about the direction of the project. And, it felt good to be highlighting how we are building on earlier investments in research by joining the dots to create a deployable measurement system and delivering the complete picture in terms of information about the condition of the structure.

Image: Infra red photograph of DIMES meeting in Ulm.

References

[Farrar & Worden, An introduction to structural health monitoring, *Phil. Trans. R Soc A*, 365:303-315, 2007](#)

[Middleton, C.A., Gaio, A., Greene, R.J. & Patterson, E.A., Towards automated tracking of initiation and propagation of cracks in aluminium alloy coupons using thermoelastic stress analysis, *Nondestructive Evaluation*, 38:18, 2019.](#)

[Christian, W.J.R., DiazDelaO, F.A. & Patterson, E.A., Strain-based damage assessment of accurate residual strength prediction of impacted composite laminates, *Composites Structures*, 184:1215-1223, 2018.](#)

The INSTRUCTIVE and [DIMES](#) projects have received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 685777 and No. 820951 respectively.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [FACTS](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [Uncategorized](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [design](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [research](#), [science](#), [strain](#) on [July 10, 2019](#).

Some problem in a different language

I spent a lot of time on trains last week. I left Liverpool on Tuesday evening for Bristol and spent Wednesday at [Airbus](#) in Filton discussing the implementation of the technologies being developed in the EU Clean Sky 2 projects [MOTIVATE](#) and [DIMES](#). On Wednesday evening I travelled to Bracknell and on Thursday gave a seminar at [Syngenta](#) on model credibility in predictive toxicology before heading home to Liverpool. But, on Friday I was on the train again, to Manchester this time, to listen to a group of my PhD students presenting their projects to their peers in our new [Centre for Doctoral Training called Growing skills for Reliable](#)

[Economic Energy from Nuclear](#), or GREEN. The common thread, besides the train journeys, is the [Fidelity And Credibility of Testing and Simulation](#) (FACTS). My research group is working on how we demonstrate the fidelity of predictions from models, how we establish trust in both predictions from computational models and measurements from experiments that are often also 'models' of the real world. The issues are similar whether we are considering the structural performance of aircraft [as on Wednesday], the impact of agro-chemicals [as on Thursday], or the performance of fusion energy and the impact of a geological disposal site [as on Friday] (see '[Hierarchical modelling in engineering and biology](#)' on March 14th, 2018) . The scientific and technical communities associated with each application talk a different language, in the sense that they use different technical jargon and acronyms; and they are surprised and interested to discover that similar problems are being tackled by communities that they rarely think about or encounter.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [FACTS](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [Airbus](#), [CDT](#), [computational modeling](#), [computational modelling](#), [DIMES](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [FACTS](#), [hierarchical models](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [model validation](#), [modeling](#), [modelling](#), [MOTIVATE](#), [MyResearch](#), [nuclear energy](#), [research](#), [simulation](#), [Syngenta](#) on [October 30, 2019](#).

When seeing nothing is a success

In November I went to Zurich twice: once for the workshop that I wrote about last week [see '[Fake facts and untrustworthy predictions](#)' on December 4th, 2019]; and, a second time for a progress meeting of the DIMES project [see '[Finding DIMES](#)' on February 6th, 2019]. The progress meeting went well. The project is on schedule and within budget. So, everyone is happy and you are wondering why I am writing about it. It was what our team was doing around the progress meeting that was exciting. A few months ago, [Airbus](#) delivered a section of an [A320](#) wing to the labs of [EMPA](#) who are our project partner in Switzerland, and the team at EMPA has been rigging the wing section for a simple bending test so that we can use it to test the integrated measurement system which we are developing in the DIMES project [see '[Joining the dots](#)' on July 10th, 2019]. Before and after the meeting, partners from EMPA, [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#), [Strain Solutions Ltd](#) and my group at the University of Liverpool were installing our prototype systems to monitor the condition of the wing when we apply bending loads to it. There is some pre-existing damage in the wing that we hope will propagate during the test allowing us to track it with our prototype systems using visible and infra-red spectrum cameras as well as electrical and optical sensors. The data that we collect during the test will allow us to develop our data processing algorithms and, if necessary, refine the system design. The final stage of the DIMES project will involve installing a series of our systems in a complete wing undergoing a structural test in the new Airbus Wing Integration Centre (AWIC) in Filton, near Bristol in the UK. The schedule is ambitious because we will need to install the sensors for our systems in the wing in the first quarter of next year, probably before we have finished all of the tests in EMPA. However, the test in Bristol probably will not start until the middle of 2020, by which time we will have refined our algorithm for data processing and be ready for the deluge of data that we are likely to receive from the test at Airbus. The difference between the two wing tests besides the level of maturity of our measurement system, is that no damage should be detected in the wing at Airbus whereas there will be detectable damage in the wing section in EMPA. So, a positive result will be a success at EMPA but a negative result, i.e. no damage detected, will be a success at Airbus.

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [design](#), [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [Airbus](#), [Big Data](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [infra-red](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [research](#), [strain](#), [Strain Solutions Ltd](#), [wing](#), [Zurich](#) on [December 11, 2019](#).

Condition-monitoring using infrared imaging

If you have travelled in Asia then you will probably have experienced having your health monitored by infrared cameras as you disembarked from your flight. It has been common practice in many Asian countries since long before the COVID-19 pandemic and perhaps will become more usual elsewhere as a means of easily identifying people with symptoms of a fever that raises their body temperature. Since, research has shown that infrared thermometers are slightly more responsive as well as quicker and easier to use than other types of skin surface thermometers [1].

In my research group, we have been using infrared cameras for many years to monitor the condition of engineering structures by evaluating the distribution of load or stress in them [see '[Counting photons to measure stress](#)' on November 18th, 2015 and '[Insidious damage](#)' on December 2nd, 2015]. In the [DIMES project](#), we have implemented a low-cost sensor system that integrates infrared and visible images with information about applied loads from point sensors, which allows the identification of initiation and tracking of damage in aircraft structures [2]. I reported in December 2019 [see '[When seeing nothing is a success](#)'] that we were installing prototype systems in a test-bench at [Empa](#). Although the restrictions imposed by the pandemic have halted our tests, we were lucky to obtain data from our sensors during the propagation of damage in the section of wing at Empa before lockdown. This is a landmark in our project and now we are preparing to install our system in test structures at [Airbus](#) once the pandemic restrictions are relaxed sufficiently. Of course, we will also be able to use our system to monitor the health of the personnel involved in the test (see the top image of one of my research team) as well as the health of the structure being tested – the hardware is the same, it's just the data processing that is different.

The image is a composite showing images from a visible camera (left) and processed data from infrared camera overlaid on the same visible image (right) from inside a wing box during a test at Empa with a crack extending from left to right with its tip surrounded by the red area in the right image. Each nut in the image is about 20 mm in diameter and a constant amplitude load at 1.25 Hz was being applied causing a wing tip displacement of 80 mm +/- 15 mm.

References

- [1] Burnham, R.S., McKinley, R.S. and Vincent, D.D., 2006. [Three types of skin-surface thermometers: a comparison of reliability, validity, and responsiveness](#). *American journal of physical medicine & rehabilitation*, 85(7), pp.553-558.
- [2] Middleton, C.A., Gaio, A., Greene, R.J. and Patterson, E.A., 2019. [Towards automated tracking of initiation and propagation of cracks in aluminium alloy coupons using thermoelastic stress analysis](#). *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*, 38(1), p.18.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd](#).

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [Asia](#), [condition monitoring](#), [COVID-19](#), [cracks](#), [damage](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#), [design](#), [Empa](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [health](#), [infra-red](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [pandemic](#), [research](#), [skin temperature](#), [strain](#), [Strain Solutions Ltd](#), [thermoelastic stress analysis](#) on [June 17, 2020](#).

Turning the screw in dentistry

Two weeks ago, I wrote about supervising PhD students and my own PhD thesis [[35 years later and still working on a PhD thesis](#) on September 16th, 2020]. The tedium of collecting data as a PhD student without digital instrumentation stimulated me to work subsequently on automation in experimental mechanics which ultimately led to projects like [INSTRUCTIVE](#) and [DIMES](#). In INSTRUCTIVE we developed low-cost digital sensors for tracking damage in components; while in DIMES we are transitioning the technology into the industrial environment using tests on full-scale aircraft systems as demonstrators. However, my research in automating and digitising measurements in experimental mechanics has not generated my most cited publications; instead, my two most cited papers describe the development and application of results in my PhD thesis to osseointegrated dental implants. One, published in 1994, describes the [Tightening characteristics for screwed joints in osseointegrated dental implants](#); while, the other published two years earlier provides a [Theoretical analysis of the fatigue life of fixture screws in osseointegrated dental implants](#). In other words, the former tells you how to tighten the screws so that the implants do not come loose and the latter how long the screws will survive before they need to be replaced – both quite useful pieces of information for dentists which perhaps explains their continued popularity.

Statistics footnote: my two most cited papers received five times as many citations in the last 18 months and also since publication than the most popular paper from my PhD thesis. The details of the three papers are given below:

Burguete, R.L., Johns, R.B., King, T. and Patterson, E.A., 1994. [Tightening characteristics for screwed joints in osseointegrated dental implants](#). *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*, 71(6), pp.592-599.

Patterson, E.A. and Johns, R.B., 1992. [Theoretical analysis of the fatigue life of fixture screws in osseointegrated dental implants](#). *The International journal of oral & maxillofacial implants*, 7(1), p.26.

Kenny, B. and Patterson, E.A., 1985. [Load and stress distribution in screw threads](#). *Experimental Mechanics*, 25(3), pp.208-213.

The INSTRUCTIVE and [DIMES](#) projects have received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 685777 and No. 820951 respectively.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Image by [володимир волощак](#) from [Pixabay](#).

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#) and tagged [dentistry](#), [digital](#), [DIMES](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [innovation](#), [INSTRUCTIVE](#), [measurements](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [osseointegrated dental implants](#), [osseointegration](#), [PhD](#), [PhD thesis](#), [research](#), [screw threads](#) on [September 30, 2020](#).

My Engineering Day

Today is 'This is Engineering' day organised by the Royal Academy of Engineering to showcase what engineers and engineering really look like, celebrate our impact on the world and shift public perception of engineering towards an appreciation that engineers are a varied and diverse group of people who are critical to solving societal challenges. You can find out more at <https://www.raeng.org.uk/events/online-events/this-is-engineering-day-2020>. I have decided to contribute to 'This is Engineering' day by describing what I do on a typical working day as an engineer.

Last Wednesday was like many other working days during the pandemic. I got up about 7am went downstairs for breakfast in our kitchen and then climbed back upstairs to my home-office in the attic of our house in Liverpool [see '[Virtual ascent of Moel Famau](#)' on April 8th, 2020]. I am lucky in that my home-office is quite separate from the living space in our house and it has a great view over the rooftops. I arrived there at about 7.45am, opened my laptop, deleted the junk email, and dealt with the emails that were urgent, interesting or could be replied to quickly. At around 8am, I closed my email and settled down to write the first draft of a proposal for funding to support our research on digital twins [see '[Tacit hurdle to digital twins](#)' on August 26th, 2020]. I had organised a meeting earlier in the week with a group of collaborators and now I had the task of converting the ideas from our discussion into a coherent programme of research. Ninety caffeine-fuelled minutes later, I had to stop for a Google Meet call with a collaborator at Airbus in Toulouse during which we agreed the wording on a statement about the impact our recent research efforts. At 10am I joined a Skype call for a progress review with a PhD student on our dual PhD programme with National Tsing Hua University in Taiwan, so we were joined by his supervisor in Taiwan where it was 6pm [see '[Citizens of the World](#)' on November 27th, 2019]. The PhD student presented some very interesting results on evaluating the waviness of fibres in carbon-fibre composite materials using ultrasound measurements which he had performed in our laboratory in Liverpool. Despite the local lockdown in Liverpool due to the pandemic, research laboratories on our campus are open and operating at reduced occupancy to allow social distancing.

After the PhD progress meeting, I had a catch-up session with my personal assistant to discuss my schedule for the next couple of weeks before joining a MS-Teams meeting with a couple of colleagues to discuss the implications of our current work on computational modelling and possible future directions. The remaining hour up to my lunch break was occupied by a conference call with a university in India with whom we are exploring a potential partnership. I participated in my capacity as Dean of the School of Engineering and joined about twenty colleagues from both institutions discussing possible areas of

collaboration in both research and teaching. Then it was back downstairs for a half-hour lunch break in the kitchen.

Following lunch, I continued in my role as Dean with a half-hour meeting with Early Career Academics in the School of Engineering followed by internal interviews for the directorship of one of our postgraduate research programmes. At 3.30pm, I was able to switch back to being a researcher and meet with a collaborator to discuss the prospects for extending our work on tracking synthetic nanoparticles into monitoring the motion of biological entities such as viruses and bacteria [see '[Modelling from the cell through the individual to the host population](#)' on May 5th 2020]. Finally, as usual, I spent the last two to three hours of my working day replying to emails, following up on the day's meetings and preparing for the following day. One email was a request for help from one of my PhD students working in the laboratory who needed a piece of equipment that had been stored in my office for safekeeping. So, I made the ten-minute walk to campus to get it for her which gave me the opportunity to talk face-to-face with one of the post-doctoral researchers in my group who is working on the [DIMES](#) project [see '[Condition-monitoring using infra imaging](#)' on June 17th, 2020]. After dinner, my wife and I walked down to the [Albert Dock](#) and along the river front to Princes Dock and back up to our house.

So that was my Engineering Day last Wednesday!

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [leadership](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [Albert Dock](#), [bacteria](#), [carbon fibre](#), [composites](#), [computational mechanics](#), [computational modeling](#), [computational modelling](#), [digital twin](#), [DIMES](#), [Engineering](#), [fibre-waviness](#), [nanoparticles](#), [National Tsing Hua University](#), [PhD](#), [PhD project](#), [PhD students](#), [Princes Dock](#), [Royal Academy of Engineering](#), [societal challenges](#), [This is Engineering Day](#), [tracking nanoparticles](#), [virus](#) on [November 4, 2020](#).

Most valued player performs remote installation

Many research programmes have been derailed by the pandemic which has closed research laboratories or restricted groups of researchers from working together to solve complex problems. Some research teams have used their problem-solving skills to find new ways of collaborating and to continue to make progress. In the [DIMES project](#) we have developed an innovative system

for detecting and monitoring the propagation of damage in aircraft structures, and prior to the pandemic, we were planning to demonstrate it on a full-scale test of an aircraft fuselage section at [Airbus](#) in Toulouse. However, the closure of our laboratories and travel restrictions across Europe have made it impossible for members of our team based in Liverpool, Chesterfield, Ulm and Zurich to meet or travel to Toulouse to set-up the demonstration. Instead we have used hours of screen-time in meetings to complete our design work and plan the installation of the system in Toulouse. These meetings often involve holding components up to our laptop cameras to show one another what we are doing. The components of the system were manufactured in various locations before being shipped to [Empa](#) in Zurich where they were assembled and the complete system was then shipped to Toulouse. At the same time, we designed a communication system that included a headset with camera, microphone and earpieces so that our colleague in Toulouse could be guided through the installation of our system by engineers in Germany, Switzerland and the UK. Amazingly, it all worked and we were half-way through the installation last month when a rise in the COVID infection rate caused a shutdown of the Airbus site in Toulouse. What we need now is remote-controlled robot to complete the installation for us regardless of COVID restrictions; however, I suspect the project budget cannot afford a robot sufficiently sophisticated to replace our Most Valued Player (MVP) in Toulouse.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd](#).

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Image: Our Most Valued Player (inset) installing a point sensor in the front section of a fuselage at Airbus in Toulouse under the remote direction of engineers in Switzerland and the UK.

This entry was posted in [design](#), [DIMES project](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [Airbus](#), [aircraft](#), [damage](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#), [Empa](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [innovation](#), [liverpool](#), [mechanics](#), [Most Valued Player](#), [MVP](#), [MyResearch](#), [remote installation](#), [research](#), [Strain Solutions Ltd](#), [Toulouse](#), [Ulm](#), [Zurich](#) on [December 2, 2020](#).

Out of the valley of death into a hype cycle?

The capability to identify damage and track its propagation in structures is important in ensuring the safe operation of a wide variety of engineering infrastructure, including aircraft structures. A few years ago, I wrote about research my group was performing, in the INSTRUCTIVE project [see [‘INSTRUCTIVE final reckoning’](#) on January 9th, 2019] with [Airbus](#) and [Strain Solutions Limited](#), to deliver a new tool for monitoring the development of damage using thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA)

[see [‘Counting photons to measure stress’](#) on November 18th, 2015]. We collected images using a TSA system while a structural component was subject to cycles of load that caused damage to initiate and propagate during a fatigue test. The series of images were analysed using a technique based on optical flow to identify apparent movement between the images which was taken as indication of the development of damage [1]. We demonstrated that our technique could indicate the presence of a crack less than a millimetre in length and even identify cracks initiating under the heads of bolts using experiments performed in our laboratory [see [‘INSTRUCTIVE update’](#) on October 4th, 2017]. However, this technique was susceptible to errors in the images when we tried to use low-cost sensors and to changes in the images caused by flight cycle loading with varying amplitude and frequency of loads. Essentially, the optical flow approach could be fooled into identifying damage propagation when a sensor delivered a noisy image or the shape of the load cycle was changed. We have now overcome this short-coming by replacing the optical flow approach with the orthogonal decomposition technique [see [‘Recognising strain’](#) on October 28th, 2015] that we developed for comparing data fields from measurements and predictions in validation processes [see [‘Million to one’](#) on November 21st, 2018]. Each image is decomposed to a feature vector and differences between the feature vectors are indicative of damage development (see schematic in thumbnail from [2]). The new technique, which we have named the differential feature vector method, is sufficiently robust that we have been able to use a sensor costing 1% of the price of a typical TSA system to identify and track cracks during cyclic loading. The underpinning research was published in December 2020 by the Royal Society [2] and the technique is being implemented in full-scale ground-tests on aircraft structures as part of the DIMES project. Once again, a piece of technology is emerging from the valley of death [see [‘Slowly crossing the valley of death’](#) on January 27th, 2021] and, without wishing to initiate the hype cycle [see [‘Hype cycle’](#) on September 23rd, 2015], I hope it will transform the use of thermal imaging for condition monitoring.

References

Figure 5. Flowchart illustrating the process used in the differential feature vector method, in which an initial TSA data field corresponding to the virgin state (top left) is compared with the current data field (top right) by representing the fields, using an identical decomposition process, as feature vectors (the elements of the feature vectors are plotted in a bar-chart (bottom)) and then the Euclidean distance between the feature vectors is calculated where a non-zero value of the distance indicates a potential change in the condition of the component.

[1] Middleton CA, Gaio A, Greene RJ & Patterson EA, [Towards automated tracking of initiation and propagation of cracks in Aluminium alloy coupons using thermoelastic stress analysis](#), J. Non-destructive Testing, 38:18, 2019.

[2] Middleton CA, Weihs M, Christian WJR, Greene RJ & Patterson EA, [Detection and tracking of cracks based on thermoelastic stress analysis](#), R. Soc. Open Sci. 7:200823, 2020.

The [INSTRUCTIVE](#) and [DIMES](#) projects have received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 685777 and No. 820951 respectively.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [INSTRUCTIVE project](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [cracks](#), [damage](#), [damage mechanics](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [hype curve](#), [image decomposition](#), [infra-red](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [model validation](#), [MyResearch](#), [orthogonal decomposition](#), [research](#), [Royal Society](#), [thermoelastic stress analysis](#), [TSA](#), [validation](#) on [February 24, 2021](#).

An upside to lockdown

While pandemic lockdowns and travel bans are having a severe impact on spontaneity and creativity in research [see '[Lacking creativity](#)' on October 28th, 2020], they have induced a high level of ingenuity to achieve the final objective of the [DIMES project](#), which is to conduct prototype demonstrations and evaluation tests of the [DIMES integrated measurement system](#). We have gone beyond the project brief by developing a remote installation system that allows local engineers at a test site to successfully set-up and run our measurement system. This has saved thousands of airmiles and several tonnes of CO2 emissions as well as hours waiting in airport terminals and sitting in planes. These savings were made by members of our project team working remotely from their bases in Chesterfield, Liverpool, Ulm and Zurich instead of flying to the test site in Toulouse to perform the installation in a section of a fuselage, and then visiting a second time to conduct the evaluation tests. For this first remote installation, we were fortunate to have our collaborator from [Airbus](#) available to support us [see '[Most valued player on performs remote installation](#)' on December 2nd, 2020]. We are about to stretch our capabilities further by conducting a remote installation and evaluation test during a full-scale aircraft test at the [Aerospace Research Centre](#) of the [National Research Council Canada](#) in Ottawa, Canada with a team who have never seen the DIMES system and knew nothing about it until about a month ago. I could claim that this remote installation and test will save another couple of tonnes of CO2; but, in practice, we would probably not be performing a demonstration in Canada if we had not developed the remote installation capability.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd](#). [Airbus](#) is our topic manager.

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#), [sustainability](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [Airbus](#), [airports](#), [Canada](#), [carbon emissions](#), [Chesterfield](#), [creativity](#), [emissions](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [GHG emissions](#), [innovation](#), [liverpool](#), [lockdown](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [Ottawa](#), [pandemic](#), [research](#), [Ulm](#), [upside](#), [Zurich](#) on [April 14, 2021](#).

Noisy progressive failure of a composite panel

Composite materials have revolutionized many fields of engineering by providing lightweight strong components whose internal structure can be tailored to optimise their load-bearing capabilities. Engineering composites consist of high-strength fibres embedded in a lightweight matrix that keeps the fibres in position and provides the shape of the component. While many composite materials have an impressive structural performance, some also exhibit spectacular failure modes with noises like guitar strings snapping when fibres start to fail and

with jagged eruptions of material appearing on the surface, as shown in the image. A year ago, I reported on our work in the [DIMES project](#), to test the capabilities of our integrated measurement system to detect and track damage in real-time in a metallic section from an aircraft wing [see '[Condition monitoring using infrared imaging](#)' on June 17th, 2020]. Last month, we completed a further round of tests at [Empa](#) to demonstrate the system's capabilities on composite structures which have been tested almost to destruction. One of the advantages of composite structures is their capability to function and bear load despite quite high levels of damage, which meant we were able to record the progressive rupture of one of our test panels during cyclic fatigue loading. Watch and listen to this [short video](#) to see and hear the material being torn apart – ignore the loud creaking and groaning from the test rig, it's the quieter sound like dead leaves being swept up.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd](#). [Airbus](#) is the topic manager on behalf of the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking.

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [composite materials](#), [composites](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [failure modes](#), [fatigue](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#) on [June 30, 2021](#).

Our last DIMES

Thirty-three months ago (see [‘Finding DIMES’](#) on February 6th, 2019) we set off at a gallop ‘to develop and demonstrate an automated measurement system that integrates a range of measurement approaches to enable damage and cracks to be detected and monitored as they originate at multi-material interfaces in an aircraft assembly’. The quotation is taken directly from the aim of the [DIMES project](#) which was originally planned and funded as a two-year research programme. Our research, in particular the demonstration element, has been slowed down by the pandemic and we resorted to two no-cost extensions, initially for three months and then for six months to achieve the project aim. Two weeks ago, we held our final review meeting, and this week we will present our latest results in the third of a series of annual workshops hosted by [Airbus](#), the project’s topic manager. The DIMES system combines visual and infrared cameras with resistance strain gauges and fibre Bragg gratings to detect 1 mm cracks in metals and damage indications in composites that are only 6 mm in diameter. We had a concept design by April 2019 (see [‘Joining the dots’](#) on July 10th, 2019) and a detailed design by August 2019. Airbus supplied us with a section of A320 wing, and we built a test-bench at Empa in Zurich in which we installed our prototype measurement system in the last quarter of 2019 (see [‘When seeing nothing is a success’](#) on December 11th, 2019). Then, the pandemic intervened and we did not finish testing until May 2021 by which time, we had also evaluated it for monitoring damage in composite A350 fuselage panels (see [‘Noisy progressive failure of a composite panel’](#) on June 30th, 2021). In parallel, we have installed our ‘DIMES system’ in ground tests on an aircraft wing at Airbus in Filton (see image) and, using a remote installation, in a cockpit at Airbus in Toulouse (see [‘Most valued player performs remote installation’](#) on December 2nd, 2020), as well as an aircraft at NRC Aerospace in Ottawa (see [‘An upside to lockdown’](#) on April 14th 2021). Our innovative technology allows condition-led monitoring based on automated damage detection and enables ground tests on aircraft structures to be run 24/7 saving about 3 months on each year-long test.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd.](#)

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author’s view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [composite materials](#), [condition monitoring](#), [cracks](#), [damage](#), [design](#), [Engineering](#), [experimental mechanics](#), [infra-red](#), [innovation](#), [mechanics](#), [MyResearch](#), [pandemic](#), [research](#), [structural integrity](#), [structures](#) on [September 22, 2021](#).

Too much of a good thing?

I wrote a couple of weeks ago about '[Our last DIMES](#)' meetings (on September 22nd, 2021). They were hybrid meetings with about half the participants attending in person and the remainder on-line. When the pandemic started we had to master the skill of conducting discussions via our laptops while sitting on our own. Now, we are learning how to include everyone in a

discussion when only half of the participants are in the physical room. One of our first steps was to re-equip our meeting rooms with higher quality video conferencing facilities so that we can see and hear one another more clearly. Unfortunately, our new equipment revealed the poor quality of the video clips we have produced during the [DIMES project](#). Nevertheless, if you have never been present during a [wing-bend test](#) or a [fatigue test on a large composite panel](#) then you might find these clips interesting (see also the [video](#) of '[Noisy progressive failure of a composite panel](#)' on June 30th 2021). We also produced an [introductory video](#) for the DIMES project which was to be first in a series of video shorts but the pandemic intervened and we have never been in the same place as our camera crew so we have not made anymore. Maybe that's a good thing because 500 hours of video are uploaded every minute to YouTube so you will not have time to watch our DIMES videos 😊.

For more short videos from our earlier projects see '[Archive video footage from EU projects](#)' on June 5th, 2019.

The [University of Liverpool](#) is the coordinator of the [DIMES project](#) and the other partners are [Empa](#), [Dantec Dynamics GmbH](#) and [Strain Solutions Ltd](#). [Airbus](#) is the topic manager on behalf of the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking.

The [DIMES](#) project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820951.

The opinions expressed in this blog post reflect only the author's view and the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This entry was posted in [DIMES project](#), [Engineering](#), [MyResearch](#), [structures](#) and tagged [aerospace](#), [composites](#), [MyResearch](#), [online conferences](#), [pandemic](#), [research](#), [videos](#), [wing bend test](#) on [October 6, 2021](#).